

A taxonomic review of *Cecilioides* (Gastropoda: Ferussaciidae) in continental Portugal

Revisión taxonómica de *Cecilioides* (Gastropoda: Ferussaciidae) en Portugal continental

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ABSTRACT

The number of *Cecilioides* species recognised from mainland Portugal has ranged from one to seven over the past 115 years, with successive authors mostly giving little or no justification for the treatment adopted. The present study is based mainly on 40 samples collected from 2001-2014, 22 of them from the Algarve. Immatures show marked interspecific differences in development of the apertural teeth (lamellae) whereas the teeth are much reduced or lacking in mature shells. Shell characters are therefore redescribed based on both immature and mature individuals as a basis for revising their taxonomic treatment. This results in *C. acicula* being recorded from much of Portugal, although there is only one record from the Algarve; it lacks shell apertural teeth at all ages or has a single small columellar tooth when immature. Two other species are known only from the Algarve, both having three prominent apertural teeth in small immature shells that are less evident at maturity: *C. barbozae* with a fusiform shell and small aperture when adult, and large teeth when immature; *C. clessini* with a more elliptical shell and larger aperture when adult, and shorter teeth when immature. These two species were found only in limestone habitats, occurring together at seven localities. *Cecilioides binodosa* appears to be based on an immature of *C. clessini*, so it is treated as a synonym. The distal genital anatomy of *C. barbozae* and *C. clessini* is described for the first time. We place these two species together in the same subgenus (*Terebrella*), separating this from *Cecilioides* (*Cecilioides*) *acicula* mainly on the basis of differences in genital anatomy.

RESUMEN

El número de especies del género *Cecilioides* reconocidas en Portugal continental ha variado entre una y siete en los últimos 115 años, generalmente con poca o ninguna justificación aportada por los autores. El presente estudio se basa principalmente en 40 muestras recogidas entre 2001 y 2014, 22 de ellas del Algarve. Ejemplares inmaduros muestran marcadas diferencias interespecíficas en el desarrollo de los dientes aberturales (laminillas), mientras que los dientes están muy reducidos o faltan en los adultos. Consecuentemente, se redescriben los caracteres conculológicos tanto en los individuos inmaduros como en los adultos, como base para la revisión de su taxonomía. Esto resulta en que *C. acicula* se registra en gran parte de Portugal, aunque sólo hay un registro del Algarve; carece de dientes aberturales en cualquier edad o tiene un solo diente columelar pequeño cuando inmaduro. Otras dos especies se conocen sólo del Algarve, ambas con tres dientes aberturales prominentes en conchas pequeñas inmaduras, menos evidentes en los adultos: *C. barbozae* con una concha fusiforme, una abertura pequeña en el adulto y los

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dientes grandes cuando inmaduro; *C. clessini* con una concha más elíptica, la abertura más grande en el adulto y los dientes más cortos cuando inmaduro. Estas dos especies sólo se encontraron en hábitats de caliza y conviven en siete localidades. *Ceciliooides binodosa* parece establecida sobre un ejemplar inmaduro de *C. clessini*, por lo que se considera una sinonimia. La anatomía del aparato genital distal de *C. barbozae* y *C. clessini* se describe por primera vez. Se juntan estas dos especies en el mismo subgénero (*Terebrella*), separando este de *Ceciliooides (Ceciliooides) acicula* principalmente sobre la base de diferencias en la anatomía genital

INTRODUCTION

The small subterranean landsnails of the genus *Ceciliooides* are often difficult to find and they have a reputation for being difficult to identify and classify into species. The only comprehensive review of the genus was by PILSBRY (1908), who often catalogued taxa without being able to pass judgment on their taxonomic validity. He commented that 'The European species of *Cæciliooides* have no doubt been multiplied beyond reason, yet without a critical study of the types it is impossible to say how many recognizable races exist. M. Bourguignat and his friends had an agreeable custom of describing "species" from single selected specimens, ignoring connecting forms.' Thus, the widespread *C. acicula* (O.F. Müller, 1774) of western Europe was split into several species in France and the Mediterranean region. However, GIUSTI (1973, 1976) and GIUSTI, MANGANELLI & SCHEMBRI (1995: 298) argued for a broad species concept by showing that in Italy there is a continuous range of intermediate forms connecting both markedly conical shells and slender shells to typical *C. acicula*. More recently, BECKMANN & FALKNER (2003) have argued that more than one Italian species is involved.

For continental Portugal, MALTZAN (1886) named three new species from the Algarve which he placed in two new subgenera: *Caecilianella (Raphidiella) Barbozae*, *Caecilianella (Terebrella) Clessini* and *Caecilianella (Terebrella) binodosa*. In his review of Portuguese snails, LOCARD (1899: 140-144) accepted Maltzan's three species and listed four

others from the Algarve, including *C. acicula*. PILSBRY (1908: 19) also accepted Maltzan's three species from the Algarve, but demoted their two subgenera to sections. However, NOBRE (1941: 167-168) treated *C. acicula* as the only Portuguese species of the genus, commenting that 'Maltzan, segundo Westerlund, ..., descreveu duas espécies provenientes de Portimão, sob o nome de *C. barbozae* e *C. binodosa*, que certamente não são mais que variedades da *C. acicula*' [i.e., *C. barbosa* and *C. binodosa* are certainly no more than varieties of *C. acicula*]. MATOS (2004: 48-49, 101) listed four Portuguese species, namely *C. acicula* and the three Portuguese endemics named by Maltzan, maintaining two separate subgenera for the latter. Surprisingly, the most recent authoritative checklist, by BANK (2011: 18) and the illustrated book by MATOS (2014: 146-149), gave only *Ceciliooides (Ceciliooides) acicula* and *Ceciliooides (Terebrella) clessini* (Maltzan, 1886) for mainland Portugal, an arrangement that is inconsistent with the Supraspecific Classification used by CLECOM (BANK, BOUCHET, FALKNER, GITTENBERGER, HAUSDORF, VON PROSCHWITZ & RIPKEN, 2001: 92) which also recognised the monotypic subgenus *Raphidiella* for *Ceciliooides barbozae*. Thus, the number of *Ceciliooides* species recognised from Portugal has ranged from one to seven over the past 115 years, but with successive authors mostly giving little or no explicit justification for the treatment adopted.

The present study aims to resolve the uncertainty regarding the number

and identity of Portuguese species of *Cecilioides*. A deliberate effort to collect population samples of this genus during fieldwork from 2001-2014 resulted in numerous specimens, corresponding to all of the more distinctive taxa hitherto reported from Portugal. Study of these shells revealed that immatures show marked interspecific differences in development of the apertural teeth (lamellae) which are much reduced or lacking in mature shells. Shell characters are therefore redescribed for immature and mature individuals of the Portuguese taxa, as a basis for revising their taxonomic treatment. The distal genital anatomy is also newly described for *C. barbozae* and *C. clessini* and compared with published accounts of that of *C. acicula*. Hence, recognition of subgenera for the Portuguese *Cecilioides* is reviewed on the basis of shell and anatomical characters.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study is based mainly on 40 samples of *Cecilioides*, 22 of them from the Algarve. Living snails were found mainly in winter or early spring when the soil was damp, usually by turning over large boulders and examining the soil beneath. Empty shells were usually present in similar sites, but sometimes also obtained by direct searching from screes, banks, ant-hills, and other places with exposed soil. Some shells of *C. acicula* were also obtained from leaf-litter samples or, occasionally, flood debris of streams, using nested 2.0 mm and 0.5 mm mesh sieves to obtain 'fines' searched later under a stereomicroscope. All shells found were retained, including small juveniles and broken material. Localities and altitudes were recorded from 2007 onwards using Garmin hand-held GPS, accurate to within 10 metres. From 2007 onwards sites were given consecutive serial numbers (e.g. P59). Habitat notes (including bedrock type and vegetation) and associated Mollusca were recorded at all sites.

Adult shells in good condition were usually distinguishable from those of immatures by the slightly thickened edge to the peristome and elongated shape, with apertural teeth (lamellae) absent or small. When well developed, the apertural 'teeth' form raised lamellae that spiral around the columellar axis, appearing as teeth when viewed end-on at the aperture. Distinction between columellar and parietal parts of the shell aperture appears to be somewhat arbitrary as the inner edge of the shell mouth when viewed from outside commonly appears evenly curved or somewhat sigmoid in shape, rather than obviously angled at the columellar-parietal junction. In immature shells with three strongly developed teeth, the two lower teeth can readily be assigned to the columella, but categorisation of the uppermost tooth as being upper columellar or lower parietal seems arbitrary.

Shells and whole specimens were studied using Meiji RZ series stereomicroscopes with illumination from twin fibre-optic swan-necks. The drawings of shells were prepared using a Meiji drawing tube on the same microscopes; measurements of shells were made with an eyepiece graticule. Details of the material studied from Portugal are listed in the Appendix. All specimens studied in detail are retained in the authors' collection.

Living specimens were drowned overnight in water, then transferred to 70% industrial methylated spirit (i.m.s.). Prior to dissection the shell was removed by breaking off fragments using fine forceps, working backwards from the aperture. Dissection to examine the distal genitalia was carried out in i.m.s. over a black surface. After locating the penis through the somewhat translucent skin, the skin was broken and organs were separated using very thin needles in conjunction with fine forceps. Proximal and distal refer to positions in relation to the ovotestis. The drawings are somewhat schematic, based on progressive separation of organs and repeated rotation of the specimens.

RESULTS AND TAXONOMY

Three species were recognised from shells, the widespread *C. acicula*, and two species endemic to the Algarve. *C. acicula* lacks shell apertural teeth at all ages or has a single small columellar tooth when immature; all of the adult shells we have seen from Portugal lack apertural teeth (Figs 1A-H). Its shell shape is rather variable from narrowly conical and somewhat fusiform to subelliptical, with the body whorl forming much more than half of the shell height (often more than two-thirds) and a correspondingly large aperture. Both of the endemic species from the Algarve have three prominent apertural teeth in small immature shells, but these are less evident to lacking at maturity. *C. barbozae* has a fusiform shell, proportionately short body whorl (typically slightly less than half of shell height) and small aperture when adult and large teeth when immature (Figs 1I-P); *C. clessini* has a more elliptical shell, body whorl forming half or slightly more than half of shell height, larger aperture when adult and smaller teeth when immature (Figs 1Q-W).

The two new subgenera introduced by MALTZAN (1886) for the endemic *Caecilianella* (now *Ceciliooides*) from the Algarve, *Rhaphidiella* and *Terebrella*, were based on shell characters, including overall shape, degree of truncation of the base of the columella and the number and degree of development of apertural teeth. PILSBRY (1908: 18-19) treated these subgenera as sections and tentatively suggested that the Madeiran *C. eulima* (Lowe, 1854) might also belong in *Rhaphidiella*. SCHILEYKO (1999: 553) again recognised *Rhaphidiella* and *Terebrella* at subgeneric rank, as did the Supraspecific Classification used by CLECOM (BANK ET AL., 2001: 92). *C. acicula* is the type of the genus *Ceciliooides* so it was placed in subgenus *Ceciliooides* A. Férussac, 1814 by SCHILEYKO (1999: 552) and CLECOM (FALKNER, BANK & VON PROSCHWITZ, 2001).

As discussed in the species accounts below, the degree of truncation of the columella varies within some of the species, and overall shell shape is reported to vary widely in *C. acicula*. The significance of apertural teeth

(Right page) Figure 1. Shells of *Ceciliooides* (Ferussaciidae) from Portugal. A-H. *C. acicula*. A-E: Beira Litoral, ca 1 km N. of Serra da Boa Viagem village, GAH 2013.P289; F-H: Estremadura, Fórnea (SE. of Alcaria), GAH & DTH 2010.P43. I-P. *C. barbozae*, from Algarve. I: ca 2 km E. of Santa Barbara de Nexe, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH 2011.P117; J: 3 km SE. of Loulé, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH 2011.P115; K: E. end of Rocha da Pena, 2011.01.28, GAH & DTH 2011.P104; L-P: ca 0.5 km S. of Bensafirim, 2011.02.06, GAH & DTH 2011.P121. Q-W. *C. clessini*, from Algarve, Cerro da Cabeça (NE. of Olhão), 2008.01.11, GAH 2008.P59. A, F, I, L, Q, R show adult shells, all other drawings are of immature shells. The adult shells are drawn with aperture facing upwards, except R which shows a slightly oblique view. All immature shells are drawn as slightly oblique views to demonstrate teeth on columellar axis. Full collection data are in the Appendix.

(Página derecha) Figura 1. Conchas de *Ceciliooides* (Ferussaciidae) de Portugal. A-H. *C. acicula*. A-E: Beira Litoral, aproximadamente 1 km N. de la aldea de Serra da Boa Viagem, GAH 2013.P289; F-H: Extremadura, Fórnea (SE de Alcaria.), GAH & DTH 2010.P43. I-P. *C. barbozae*, del Algarve. I: unos 2 km E. de Santa Bárbara de Nexe, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH 2011.P117; J: a 3 km SE. de Loulé, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH 2011.P115; K: Extremo E. de Rocha da Pena, 28/01/2011, GAH & DTH 2011.P104; L-P: aproximadamente 0,5 km S. de Bensafirim, 06/02/2011, GAH & DTH 2011.P121. Q-W. *C. clessini*, del Algarve, Cerro da Cabeça (NE. de Olhão), 11/01/2008, GAH 2008.P59. A, F, I, L, Q, R representan conchas adultos, todos los demás dibujos son de conchas inmaduras. Las conchas adultas se dibujan con la abertura hacia arriba, a excepción de R que muestra una vista ligeramente oblicua. Las conchas inmaduras se dibujan en vista ligeramente oblicua para mostrar los dientes en el eje de la columela. Los datos completos de recolección se indican en el Apéndice.

(lamellae) in delimiting subgenera in *Cecilioides* is also uncertain since at least the youngest immature shells of most of the species appear to at least sometimes possess teeth, which often do not show at all in fully mature shells (Fig. 1). Interspecific variation in development of teeth (lamellae) is conspicuous within some other European pulmonate genera, notably *Vertigo* O.F. Müller, 1773, *Truncatellina* R.T. Lowe, 1852 and *Chondrina* Reichenbach, 1828, but does not necessarily lead to recognition of subgenera.

New information on the structure of the distal genitalia is also presented in the species accounts below for *C. (Raphidiella) barbozae* and *C. (Terebrella) clessini*, which is compared to published information on *C. acicula* (Fig. 2). Both species differ from *C. acicula* in having the narrow distal part of the penis shorter than the wide proximal part (not *vice versa*), the wide proximal penis

more elongate (less broadly ovate), and the insertion of the bursa copulatrix duct placed in a more distal position on the female tract so that the free oviduct is less short compared to length of the vagina (i.e. *C. acicula* has a proportionately much shorter free oviduct and a much longer vagina than the other two species). All of the differences from *C. acicula* showed greater development in *C. clessini* than in *C. barbozae*, perhaps because our material of the latter species was not fully mature.

A phylogenetic study of many more species, using additional data that ideally include those from molecular characters, is desirable to form a secure basis for (sub) generic classification in *Cecilioides*. In the meantime, we place the two Algarve species together in the same subgenus (*Terebrella*), separating this from *Cecilioides (Cecilioides) acicula* mainly on the basis of differences in genital anatomy.

Family FERUSSACIIDAE Bourguignat, 1883
Genus *Cecilioides* A. Férussac, 1814

Type species: *Bulinus acicula* Bruguière, 1792 = *Buccinum acicula* O.F. Müller, 1774 (by monotypy, *vide* SCHILEYKO, 1999: 552, BANK, GROH & RIPKEN, 2002: 134).

Syn. *Styloides* Fitzinger, 1833; *Macrospira* Swainson, 1840; *Belonis* W. Hartmann, 1841; *Caecilioides* Herrmannsen, 1846; *Caeciliana* Bourguignat, 1856; *Aciculina* Westerlund, 1887.

PILSBRY (1908: 1) amended the name to *Cæcilioides*, but WATSON (1928: 239, footnote 1) argued that Férussac's original spelling should be retained and it was adopted by PILSBRY (1946: 184). Opinion 335 of the I.C.Z.N. placed *Cecilioides* on the Official List of Names of Genera in Zoology, attributing the gender as feminine. FALKNER, RIPKEN & FALKNER (2002: 116, note 181) pointed out that although the feminine gender must now prevail, it was apparently assigned in error since the I.C.Z.N. Code (Art. 30.1.4.4) states that all names ending in *-oides* are substantiated adjectives and are masculine. This does not directly affect nomenclature of the taxa recognised here from mainland Portugal, since the epithet *acicula* is a noun in apposition (signifying a 'needle'),

whereas *clessini* is a noun in the genitive case formed from the personal name Clessin (masculine). The original spelling of the name *barbozae* is more puzzling, but it was apparently formed from the personal name Barboza, with suffix *-ae* used either as a feminine ending (in accordance with ICZN Art. 31 (a) (ii)), or because it was treated as a Latin or latinized name (in accordance with Art. 31 (a) (i) and Examples). The latter alternative is more probable, since the zoologist most likely to be honoured was José Vicente Barboza du Bocage (1823-1907) who was curator of the Natural Museum of Lisbon and known as 'Barboza du Bocage'. However, MALTZAN (1886: 26) does not state who was involved, whether male or female, nor does he state whether the family

name was regarded as Latin, latinized or modern. Therefore, under ICZN Art. 32 (b) and (c) we must regard *barbozae* as the “correct original spelling”, as did such critical early authors as WESTER-

LUND (1887: 182), LOCARD (1899: 143) and PILSBRY (1908: 19). The genus was placed in Subfamily Ferussaciinae by CLECOM (BANK *ET AL.*, 2001: 92; FALKNER *ET AL.*, 2001).

Subgenus *Cecilioides* A. Férussac, 1814
Cecilioides acicula (O.F. Müller, 1774)

Buccinum acicula O.F. Müller, 1774 (pp. 150-151). Type locality: Thangelstedt (Thuringia, Germany).

Achatina acicula. (Lam.): Silva (1871: 257).

Cæcilianella acicula, Müller: Locard (1899: 140), *pars*?

Cæciloides acicula (Müller): Pilsbry (1908: 9, pl. 1).

Cæcilianella acicula (Müller): Nobre (1941: 167), *pars*, excluding *C. barbozae* and *C. binodosa*.

Cecilioides (*Cecilioides*) *acicula* (Müller, 1774): Schileyko (1999: 553-554).

Cecilioides (*Cecilioides*) *acicula* (O.F. Müller 1774): Bank, Groh & Ripken (2002: 107).

Cecilioides (*Cecilioides*) *acicula* (O.F. Müller 1774): Matos (2004: 48, 2014: 146).

For fuller synonymies of this species or species-group see: PILSBRY (1908: 9-13), GERMAIN (1930: 330-333), ALZONA (1971: 112-113), GIUSTI, MANGANELLI & SCHEMBRI (1995: 294), SYSOEV & SCHILEYKO (2009: 111).

Specimens studied: 88 shells from 19 localities in mainland Portugal. Additional material from localities in Ireland (1), Great Britain (3), France (2), Malta (2) and Spain (9).

Diagnosis (see Figs 1A-H): Immature Portuguese shells lack any apertural teeth (lamellae) or have a single tooth on the upper part of the columella. The single tooth forms a spiral lamella (‘fold’) which was figured by WATSON (1928: pl. 5 fig. 3), who noted that it disappears when the snail is half-grown, although it persists until a later stage in some forms (until the shell matures in *C. liesvillei* (Bourguignat, 1856) which GERMAIN, 1930: 330-331 figured and treated as a valid species). Adult shells are sometimes difficult to distinguish from those of the two following species, which are endemic to the Algarve. However, the lack of any trace of a tooth on the columella is indicative of *C. acicula*. Adult shells of *C. clessini* are commonly larger and broader, more elliptical in outline. Adult shells of *C. barbozae* typically show two teeth on the lower part of the columellar axis, at least in oblique views into the mouth, with a rather deep concave depression between them. They are sometimes also more obviously fusiform.

Variation: *Cecilioides acicula* is a difficult species or species-group, in which numerous nominal taxa from the

Mediterranean region still need revision (cf. BECKMANN & FALKNER, 2003). However, as noted above, GIUSTI (1973: 216-222, 1976: 231-244) and GIUSTI *ET AL.* (1995: 298) summarised evidence from Italy that a continuous spectrum of intermediate forms connects both markedly conical shells and slender shells to those commonly regarded as typical of *C. acicula*, implying that a broad species concept is appropriate. Shell size varies markedly between samples from different localities in mainland Portugal, with the largest adult shells in the small samples available reaching a maximum of 5.9 × 1.8 mm (Baixo Alentejo, ca 2 km W. of Pomarão, 2014.P383) but minima of 4.2 × 1.2 mm (Algarve, just NW. of Almádena, 2011.P122) and 4.0 × 1.2 mm (Beira Litoral, ca 1 km N. of Serra da Boa Viagem village, 2013.P289).

Other shell figs: PILSBRY (1908: pl. 1), WATSON (1928: pl. 5), GIUSTI (1973, 1976), KERNEY & CAMERON (1979), KERNEY, CAMERON & JUNGBLUTH (1983), MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, ROBLES CUENCA, MARTÍNEZ-LÓPEZ & RODRIGUEZ BABÍO (1991: 411, 413), GIUSTI *ET AL.* (1995: 294-

295), SCHILEYKO (1999: 554), RUIZ, CÁRCABA, PORRAS & ARRÉBOLA (2006: 209), BECKMANN (2007: 70).

Genital anatomy: None were dissected during the present study, but good figures and descriptions are available from WATSON (1928: pl. 5), GIUSTI (1973, 1976), MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ *ET AL.* (1991: 419) and SCHILEYKO (1999: 554). To facilitate comparisons, the drawing of the distal genitalia from the last of these accounts is copied as our Fig. 2A. The published accounts are consistent in recording the following characters of the distal genitalia: genital atrium short; penis consisting of narrow tube distally, widening proximally and rather abruptly to a much wider distal section that is of similar length or shorter and contains a muscular verge; penial retractor muscle inserting on proximal end of penis very close to position where distal end of vas deferens is inserted; vas deferens long, narrow throughout or wider only close to the proximal end, passing distally alongside penis to penial-vaginal angle, then returning proximally alongside female tract to distal end of prostate; vagina rather narrow, much longer than free oviduct, much shorter than penis; bursa copulatrix duct short; bursa copulatrix rather small, oval or elliptical, lying alongside prostate. The two Spanish specimens studied by MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ *ET AL.* (1991: 419, figs 8A, B) had the vas deferens wider close to its proximal end, whereas WATSON (1928: pl. 5, fig. 5) and SCHILEYKO (1999: 554, fig. 730B) portray it as narrow throughout. WATSON (1928: pl. 5, p. 229) recorded that the penial retractor muscle is attached to the columellar muscle, not to the diaphragm as it is in *Ferussacia* Risso, 1826; he also noted that the genital pore opens on the right-hand side of the head. SCHILEYKO (1999: 554) noted that the vagina has partly glandular walls forming a perivaginal gland.

Range in Portugal: Our own records are concentrated in limestone districts of western-central Portugal (Beira Litoral, Estremadura, Ribatejo) where we have carried out extensive fieldwork, with one on limestone in the W. Algarve and a few over calcium-poor rocks in the east and south-east (Beira Baixa, Baixo Alentejo)

(Fig. 3A, Appendix). It doubtless also occurs in northern Portugal and other regions of central Portugal, since NOBRE (1941: 168) lists Monção, Barcelos, Vimioso and Porto in the north, and Lisboa and Cezimbra (Sesimbra) among localities further south for his very broadly defined taxon. The map given by MATOS (2014: 146) gives ten records from the S. Algarve that are likely to be due at least in part to misidentification of the endemic Algarve species of the genus; her Figura 109 labelled as *C. acicula* shows three shells of *C. clessini* from Faro; Figura 110 and Figura 111 also show *C. clessini* from Faro, although labelled respectively as *Caecilianella liesvillei* Bourguignat and *Caecilianella nanodea* Bourguignat.

Range elsewhere: The extent of the native range is uncertain because the species is widely introduced and most fossil records have little value in this subterranean species that burrows to considerable depths. Apparently native in much of W., C. and S. Europe, from Ireland, England, S. Sweden, Germany, Poland, Czech Republic, Austria, the Balkans and Ukraine southwards to the Iberian Peninsula, Italy and Malta, extending eastwards to Turkey, Caucasus and Central Asia (Kopet Dagh to Pamiro-Altai: SYSOEV & SCHILEYKO, 2009: 111). It is widespread over much of the Iberian Peninsula, although absent from large areas in C. Spain (MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ *ET AL.*, 1991: 420; ALTONAGA, GÓMEZ, MARTÍN, PRIETO, PUENTE & RALLO, 1994: 261). As an introduction it is reported from Latvia, Azores, Canary Is., N. America (U.S.A., Ontario), Bermuda, Barbados, Argentina, S. Africa, New Zealand and Tasmania (PILSBRY, 1908: 9, 1946: 186; BARKER, 1999; BIELER & SLAPCINSKY, 2000; BANK, GROH & RIPKEN 2002: 107; BONHAM, 2005; FORSYTH, OLDHAM & SCHUELER, 2008; ŠTEFFEK, STALAŽS & DREIJERS, 2008).

Habitats and ecology: Of 17 localities where it was found *in situ* in mainland Portugal, 11 were over limestone, 4 over slate, 1 over shale and 1 associated with calcareous masonry of ruins. It was the only *Cecilioidea* found at 18 localities in mainland Portugal, but coexisted with *C. barbozae* at a single locality in the W. Algarve.

Subgenus *Terebrella* Maltzan, 1886

Type species: *Caecilianella Clessini* Maltzan, 1886 (p. 27), by original designation.

Syn. *Rhaphidiella* Maltzan, 1886 (p. 26), type species: *Caecilianella Barbozae* Maltzan, 1886 (p. 26), by original designation.

Since MALTZAN (1886) published the genus-group names *Rhaphidiella* and *Terebrella* in the same work on the same date and no subsequent author has hitherto considered them to be synonyms, as First Revisers (I.C.Z.N.

Code, Art. 24) we regard *Terebrella* as having precedence over *Rhaphidiella*, because in our material the anatomical differences from *Cecilioides* s. str. are more pronounced in *C. clessini* than in *C. barbozae*.

Cecilioides barbozae (Maltzan, 1886)

Caecilianella (Subgen. *Rhaphidiella*) *Barbozae* Maltzan, 1886 (p. 26). Type locality: Portimão, Algarve (Portugal).

Cionella Barbozae: Westerlund (1887: 182).

Caecilianella nanodea Bourguignat: Locard (1899: 142) (non Bourguignat, 1856). The description and record from Faro (Algarve) suggest mature shells of this species, without visible apertural teeth.

Caecilianella Barbozae, Von Maltzan: Locard (1899: 143).

Cecilioides (Section *Rhaphidiella*) *barbozae* (Maltzan): Pilsbry (1908: 19).

Caecilianella acicula (Müller): Nobre (1941: 167), *pars*.

Cecilioides (*Rhaphidiella*) *barbozae* (Maltzan, 1886): Schileyko (1999: 553).

Cecilioides (*Rhaphidiella*) *barbozae* (von Maltzan 1886): Matos (2004: 49).

Specimens studied: 54 shells and 7 whole specimens from 10 localities in the Algarve, Portugal.

Diagnosis (see Figs 1I-P): Immature shells have three well developed apertural teeth that are conspicuously larger than those of *C. clessini*, whereas *C. acicula* has no teeth or only one. Compared to *C. clessini*, adult shells are mostly smaller and proportionately narrower (maximum width 0.71-1.25 mm, cf. 1.17-1.59 mm), with more fusiform, less elliptical outline, with a proportionately smaller aperture (30.4-41.8% , cf. 37.1-47.9 of total shell height) and more obvious apertural teeth. Typically, they show two teeth on the lower part of the columellar axis, at least in oblique views into the mouth, with a rather deep concave depression between them that is lacking in *C. clessini*.

MALTZAN (1886: 26) followed by Pilsbry (1908: 5) stated that *C. barbozae* differs from *C. acicula* and *C. clessini* in having the base of the columella not truncate or very indistinctly so. However, it is often conspicuously trun-

cated in *C. barbozae* (e.g. Figs 1I, 1J) although not in other shells of that species (e.g. Fig. 1P), and variable in the other species (cf. Figs 1A and 1F for *C. acicula*, 1Q and 1W for *C. clessini*). However, the extent to which truncation of the columella is visible tends to vary according to the angle from which the aperture is examined, with oblique views into the aperture often showing conspicuous truncation when none is visible from a frontal view.

Variation: Our shells from the western Algarve at Bensafrim (Figs 1L-P), Sagres and Almadena are conspicuously larger than those from the central Algarve (Figs 1I-K). Measurements (mm) of adult shells from localities east of Portimão (P108, P115, P117, P365B, P366) are: height 2.53-3.45 (mean 3.083, standard deviation 0.260, n = 10), width 0.71-0.95 (mean 0.844, standard deviation 0.066, n = 10), aperture height 0.95-1.22 (mean 1.070, standard deviation 0.092, n = 9), aperture

height/shell height $\times 100 = 30.4\text{--}41.3\%$ (mean 34.59%). Similar measurements from localities west of Portimão (P121, P125) are: height 3.97–4.32 (mean 4.123, standard deviation 0.121, $n = 6$), width 1.15–1.25 (mean 1.183, standard deviation 0.043, $n = 6$), aperture height 1.47–1.72 (mean 1.590, standard deviation 0.094, $n = 6$), aperture height/shell height $\times 100 = 35.2\text{--}41.8\%$ (mean 38.65%). The type specimen from Portimão measured $3 \times \frac{3}{4}$ mm with aperture height 1 mm (Maltzan, 1886: 27), which corresponds to our measurements of shells from further east. There is little overlap in shell measurements with the larger shells from west of Portimão, but taxonomic separation of the latter populations does not appear to be justified. Although our data suggest the western populations usually have a proportionately larger shell aperture in addition to larger shell size, they do not differ in other respects. Comparable variation in shell size between different populations regarded as conspecific has already been noted above for *C. acicula* from Portugal. SCHILEYKO (1999: 553) gives another figure of the shell.

Living animals: have the entire body white.

Genital anatomy: Two dissected during the present study provide information on

the anatomy of the distal genitalia (Fig. 2B). The small size of their genitalia may suggest that neither of the specimens studied was completely mature. Several differences are apparent from the characters of *C. acicula* described above: the penis has the narrow distal part shorter, the wide proximal part proportionately longer and elliptical or narrowly ovate rather than shortly ovate; the vas deferens is slightly thicker throughout much of the proximal one-third of its length, rather than uniformly narrow almost throughout (or markedly thickened only close to the proximal end: see above); the bursa copulatrix duct inserts further down the female tract, so that the free oviduct is proportionately somewhat longer, although still shorter than the vagina.

Range: Endemic in the Algarve, where it apparently occurs over most of the region with limestone bedrock, from near Sagres in the west, eastwards to the vicinity of Moncarapacho and inland to Rocha da Pena (Fig. 3B, Appendix).

Habitats and ecology: All ten of the localities studied in the Algarve were at sites with soil present over limestone bedrock; the soil layer was deep at some sites, thinner at others. It coexisted with *C. clessini* at seven of them and with *C. acicula* at one locality.

Cecilioides clessini (Maltzan, 1886)

Caecilianella (Subgen. *Terebrella*) *Clessini* Maltzan, 1886 (p. 27). Original type locality given as “Portimão et Tavira, Algarve” (Portugal). Syntype in Forschungsinstitut Senckenburg, Germany, registered as SMF 157223, labelled as from “Portimao, Algarve” on original label of O. Boettger (Dr R. Janssen *in litt.*), figured by Matos (2014: 149, figura 113), designated here as Lectotype.

Caecilianella (Subgen. *Terebrella*) *binodosa* Maltzan, 1886 (p. 27). Type locality: Portimão, Algarve (Portugal). The description appears to be based on immature shells.

Cionella Clessini: Westerlund (1887: 183).

Cionella binodosa: Westerlund (1887: 183).

Caecilianella Castroiana Locard, 1899 (p. 141). Type locality: Faro [Algarve]. The description suggests *C. clessini* with no visible apertural teeth, a condition very common in this species where teeth are consistently well developed only in small immatures. Matos (2014: 149, Figura 112) figures a shell from Faro attributed to this taxon from Museu de História Natural (Zoologia) da Faculdade de Ciências da Universidade do Porto, Portugal (MZUP.CJSC.96).

Caecilianella Clessini, Von Maltzan: Locard (1899: 143).

Caecilianella binodosa, Von Maltzan: Locard (1899: 143).

Cæcilioides (Section *Terebrella*) *clessini* (Maltzan): Pilsbry (1908: 19).

Cæcilioides (Section *Terebrella*) *binodosa* (Maltzan): Pilsbry (1908: 19).

Caecilianella acicula (Müller): Nobre (1941: 167), *pars*.

Figure 2. Drawings of distal genitalia of *Cecilioides* (Ferussaciidae). A: *C. acicula* from Daghestan, eastern Caucasus redrawn from SCHILEYKO (1999: 554, fig. 730B); B: *C. barbozae*, Portugal, Algarve, just NW. of Almádena, 2011.02.06, GAH & DTH 2011.P122; C: *C. clessini*, Portugal, Algarve, E. end of Rocha da Pena, 2011.01.28, GAH & DTH 2011.P104. Scale bars for B and C represent 1.0 mm. Abbreviations: bc: bursa copulatrix; bcd: bursa copulatrix duct; ga: genital atrium; pe: penis; prm: penis retractor muscle; sod: spermoviduct; va: vagina; vd: vas deferens.

Figura 2. Dibujos de genitales distales de *Cecilioides* (Ferussaciidae). A: *C. acicula* de Daguestán, Cáucaso oriental, redibujado de SCHILEYKO (1999: 554, fig 730B); B: *C. barbozae*, Portugal, Algarve, justo al NO. de Almádena, 06/02/2011, GAH & DTH 2011.P122; C: *C. clessini*, Portugal, Algarve, extremo E. de Rocha da Pena, 28/01/2011, GAH & DTH 2011.P104. Las barras de escala para B y C representan 1,0 mm. Abreviaturas: bc: bursa copulatrix; bcd: conducto de la bursa copulatrix; ga: atrio genital; pe: pene; prm: músculo retractor del pene; sod: spermoviduct; va: vagina; vd: vaso deferente.

Cecilioides (*Terebrella*) *clessini* (Maltzan, 1886): Schileyko (1999: 553).

Cecilioides (*Terebrella*) *clessini* (von Maltzan 1886): Matos (2004: 49).

Cecilioides (*Terebrella*) *binodosa* (von Maltzan 1886): Matos (2004: 49).

Cecilioides (*Terebrella*) *clessini* (von Maltzan 1886): Matos (2014: 148-149, figs 112, 113); as noted in our account of *C. acicula* above, although Figuras 109-111 (*op. cit.*, p. 147) are labelled as other species, they all depict *C. clessini*.

[*Cæcilianella liesvillei*, Bourguignat cited by Locard (1899: 141) (non Bourguignat, 1856), named as a taxon with an apertural tooth, from Estoy (Algarve) can probably be referred to *C. barbozae* or *C. clessini*.]

Specimens studied: 200 shells and 32 whole specimens from 10 localities in the Algarve, Portugal.

Diagnosis (see Figs 1Q-W): Small immature shells have three apertural teeth that are smaller than those of *C. barbozae*, so some shells appear to have only two teeth; *C. acicula* has no teeth or only one. Compared to *C. barbozae*, adult shells are usually larger, proportionately broader (narrowly elliptical in outline with penultimate whorl nearly as wide as body whorl, not fusiform with an

obviously narrower penultimate whorl), with a proportionately larger aperture and apertural teeth much less obvious, or indeed short, weak, and visible only in an oblique view. The rather deep concave depression present in *C. barbozae* between two teeth on the columellar axis is lacking in *C. clessini*. See the account of *C. barbozae* above for comparative measurements.

Figure 3. Maps of the distribution in mainland Portugal of *Ceciliooides* (Ferussaciidae) based on 10×10 km squares of the U.T.M. grid. A, *C. acicula*; B, *C. barbozae*; C, *C. clessini*. Closed circles represent specimens studied by the authors (see Appendix for details); open squares represent original localities from MALTZAN (1886) (with Tavira plotted as 29SPB10 because limestone outcrops in that square).

Figura 3. Mapas de distribución en Portugal continental de *Ceciliooides* (Ferussaciidae) basados en cuadrículas UTM de 10×10 km. A, *C. acicula*; B, *C. barbozae*; C, *C. clessini*. Los círculos rellenos representan ejemplares estudiados por los autores (véase el Apéndice para detalles); los cuadrados abiertos representan localidades originales de MALTZAN (1886) (con Tavira marcada como 29SPB10 porque los afloramientos calizos están en dicha cuadrícula).

Variation: Shells from Cerro da Cabeça (NE. of Olhão) (Figs 1Q-W) and Rocha da Pena (e.g. Fig. 4) are larger and broader than those from most other localities, giving an elliptical outline, suggestive of *Hohenwartiana* species (which differ anatomically in having a diverticulum on the penis: MARTÍNEZ-ORTÍ, 2002: 6, figs 11-13). However, other populations are intermediate in shape. Measurements (mm) of representative adult shells from six populations (P59, P104, P107, P118, P119, P365B) are: height 3.75-5.10 (mean 4.436, standard deviation 0.486, $n = 12$), width 1.17-1.59 (mean 1.348, 0.145, $n = 12$), aperture height 1.69-2.23 (mean 1.883, standard deviation 0.154, $n = 12$). The extent of shell size variation involved is thus approximately comparable to that noted above for *C. acicula*. Other shell figures are given by ZILCH (1959-1960: 338, fig.

1240), SCHILEYKO (1999: 553, showing the columellar tooth in a higher position than normal in our material of the species) and MATOS (2014: see notes in synonymy above).

Living animals: have the exposed parts of the body white and somewhat translucent. Specimens preserved in alcohol have the mantle white externally and the parts of the body inside the spire of the shell whitish or light brown in different individuals. Living snails have a longitudinal groove along the dorsal midline and upper tentacles that are somewhat swollen near the apex, lacking eyes (Fig. 4). These features are very similar to those described for *C. acicula* by ADAMS (1900: 298-299), who believed that a colourless eyeball was present in that species, but WATSON (1928: 220) reinterpreted this as a discoidal area of columnar epithelium

Figure 4. Photograph of a living *Cecilioides clessini*, taken in field, Portugal, Algarve, E. end of Rocha da Pena, 2011.01.28, GAH & DTH 2011.P104.

Figura 4. Fotografía de un *Cecilioides clessini* vivo, tomada en el medio natural, Portugal, Algarve, extremo E. de Rocha da Pena, 28/01/2011, GAH & DTH 2011.P104.

capping the large olfactory organ which is responsible for slight swelling in the tip of the upper tentacle.

Genital anatomy: Two dissected during the present study provide information on the anatomy of the distal genitalia (Fig. 2C). Both had proportionately large genitalia, suggesting they were mature. Their distal genitalia differed from the description given above for those of *C. acicula* in several respects, being more similar to those of *C. barbozae*. However, in *C. clessini* the differences from *C. acicula* were developed to a greater extent than in *C. barbozae*, perhaps because the specimens of the latter species had genitalia that were not fully mature. Thus, in *C. clessini* the narrow distal part of the penis was very short compared to the wide elongate-ovate proximal part; the vas deferens was very narrow throughout its distal part (alongside the penis) but conspicuously wider (as wide as the vagina) in its proximal part (alongside the female tract); the insertion of the bursa copula-

trix duct on the female tract was more distally located, so that the free oviduct was nearly as long as the vagina.

Range: Endemic in the Algarve, where it is known over much of the region with limestone bedrock, except towards the western end. Our own records extend from Caneiros (S. of Ferragudo) eastwards to the vicinity of Moncarapacho and inland to Rocha da Pena (Fig. 3C, Appendix). The original type localities at Portimão and Tavira thus mark the approximate western and eastern limits of the known range. Although limestone extends westwards from Portimão to Cabo São Vicente, and *C. barbozae* is recorded westwards to near Sagres, there are no records of *C. clessini* from these western regions.

Habitats and ecology: All ten of the localities studied in the Algarve were at sites where soil was present over limestone bedrock. It occurred with *C. barbozae* at seven localities, but not at any where *C. acicula* was present.

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Appendix. List of material studied from Portugal

Data are listed in sequence for each species as Province, locality name, U.T.M. grid reference (or latitude and longitude), U.T.M. hectad (10 × 10 km square), habitat, altitude (metres), date (yyyy.mm.dd), collector's initials, collector's field number, collection where housed, number of shells or whole specimens. To save space, identical information on species and Province is not repeated; a semi-colon is used only to separate each sample. Abbreviations: CGAH = Collection of G.A. & D.T. Holyoak; DTH = D.T. Holyoak. GAH = G.A. Holyoak, imm. = immature, sh = shell or shells, spm = whole specimens preserved in alcohol (industrial methylated spirit).

Cecilioides acicula, Algarve: just NW. of Almádena, 29S 052017/410618, 29SNB20, nearly flat ground over limestone with short herbs and grasses, scattered rocks, patchy low scrub, 47 m, 2011.02.06, GAH & DTH, 2011.P122, CGAH, 1 sh (almost certainly this species); Baixo Alentejo: ca 1 km W. of Pomarao, 29S 0629/4157, 29SPB25, slaty slopes, ca 10 m, 2014.04.18, GAH, 2014.P382, CGAH, 1 sh; ca 2 km W. of Pomarao, 29S 0629/4158, 29SPB25, slate scree, ca 14 m, 2014.04.18, GAH, 2014.P383, CGAH, 26 sh; near Ermida das Pazes, ca 2 km SE. of Vila Verde de Ficalho, 29S 06515/42002, 29SPC50, small N.-facing roadside cutting of shaly rock, patchy grasses and herbs, 195 m, 2013.10.29, GAH & DTH, 2013.P340, CGAH, 1 sh; Beira Baixa: by Rio Zêzere and N238 ENE. of Dornes, 29S 05644/44037, 29SNE60, rocky (slate) cuttings and slopes by road and reservoir, 143 m, 2011.08.05, GAH & DTH, 2011.P177, CGAH, 1 sh; NW. side of Rio Ocreza by N233 ca 2 km W. of Taberna Seca, 29S 06204/44108, 29SPE21, under rocks on slaty banks, 206 m, 2013.03.28, GAH, 2013.P297, CGAH, 2 sh (live-collected); Beira Litoral: Vale de Poios (ca 1.5 km SE. of Poios), 29S 05380/44257, 29SNE32, rocky limestone crags and slopes (N.-facing), near and in valley bottom, ca 140 m, 2012.08.17, GAH & DTH, 2012.P260, CGAH, 1 sh; by N348 SE. of Almofter, 29S 05498/44099, 29SNE40, low limestone crags, ca 370 m, 2009.06.10, GAH, 2009.P3, not kept; 0.5 km S. of IC8 at ca 2 km WNW. of Ansião, 29S 054642/441843, 29SNE41, ledges on N.-facing limestone crag, with scrub above, ca 190 m, 2010.09.26, GAH & DTH, 2010.P75, CGAH, 7 sh; ca 0.5 km S. of IC8 at ca 1.5 km WNW. of Ansião, 29S 05466/44185, 29SNE41, drift debris at edge of dried stream, ca 194 m, 2010.09.26, GAH & DTH, 2010.P73c, CGAH, 4 sh; ca 1 km E. of Alvorge, 29S 0547/4425, 29SNE42, rocky limestone slopes, 2014.04.10, GAH, 2014.P374, CGAH, 3 sh; ca 3 km SW. of Chão de Couce, 29S 05502/44145, 29SNE51, under stones on limestone slopes, 456 m, 2014.04.28, GAH, 2014.P384, CGAH, 1 sh; just NE. of Cabo Mondego, 29T 05086/44491, 29TNE04, scrub-covered slopes with low limestone outcrops, ca 78 m, 2010.08.23, GAH, 2010.P70, not kept, 1 imm. sh; ca 1 km N. of Serra da Boa Viagem village, 29T 05121/44495, 29TNE14, limestone quarry, grassland, roadside, 216 m, 2013.03.02, GAH, 2013.P289, CGAH, 10 sh; near Capela Santo Antonio Degracias, ca 1 km NNW. of Degracias, 29T 0540/4430, 29TNE43, limestone grassland and rocky slopes with low crags, ca 400 m, 2014.03.10, GAH & DTH, 2014.P352, CGAH, 8 sh; Estremadura: Serra de Montejunto, 29S 04950/43382, 29SMD93, rocky limestone slopes and crags (low scrub and herb rich), ca 400 m, 2010.04.19, GAH, 2010.P34, not kept; Fórnea (SE. of Alcaria), 29S 05170/43789, 29SND17, flood debris of small stream, ca 275 m, 2010.05.02, GAH & DTH, 2010.P43, CGAH, 10 sh; ca 1.5 km SE. of Livramento, 29S 05170/43806, 29SND18, rocky limestone slopes facing E. below crag, with evergreen oak woodland, 290 m, 2010.08.06, GAH & DTH, 2010.P64, CGAH, 7 sh; Ribatejo: Convento de Cristo, just W. of Tomar, 29S 05499/43839, 29SND48, convent and castle walls and ruins, 126 m, 2011.08.05, GAH & DTH, 2011.P175, CGAH, 4 sh.

Cecilioides barbozae, Algarve: ca 2 km NW. of Sagres, 29S 05045/40971, 29SNA09, flat ground with patchy bushes, grassland and scattered limestone rocks, 15 m,

2011.02.07, GAH & DTH, 2011.P125, CGAH, 1 sh; just NW. of Almádena, 29S 052017/410618, 29SNB20, nearly flat ground over limestone with short herbs and grasses, scattered rocks, patchy low scrub, 47 m, 2011.02.06, GAH & DTH, 2011.P122, CGAH, 7 spm; *ca* 0.5 km S. of Bensafrim, 29S 05237/41116, 29SNB21, S.-facing limestone slope, with bare soil and low herbs, scattered bushes, 76 m, 2011.02.06, GAH & DTH, 2011.P121, CGAH, 16 sh; SSE. of church at Bensafrim, 37°09'N 8°44'W, 29SNB21, limestone slopes with crags and scrub, *ca* 70 m, 2001.06.01, GAH, 2001.s.n., CGAH, 9 sh; Caneiros (S. of Ferragudo), 29S 0543/4106, 29SNB40, rocky limestone slopes with low scrub by coast, *ca* 23 m, 2014.03.23, GAH, 2014.P366, CGAH, 15 sh; 3 km SE. of Loulé, 29S 058884/410560, 29SNB80, rocky limestone slope with patchy cover of low bushes, 85 m, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH, 2011.P115, CGAH, 1 sh; *ca* 3 km W. of Querenca, 29S 0588/4117, 29SNB81, limestone scree, *ca* 146 m, 2014.03.22, GAH, 2014.P365B, CGAH, 3 sh; E. end of Rocha da Pena, 29S 05803/41234, 29SNB82, rocky limestone slope and plateau with patches of bushes, 460 m, 2011.01.28, GAH & DTH, 2011.P104, CGAH, 3 sh; *ca* 2 km E. of Santa Barbara de Nexe, 29S 059428/410732, 29SNB90, rocky limestone hill-slopes with patchy low scrub, 261 m, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH, 2011.P117, CGAH, 3 sh; by N398 *ca* 2 km N. of Moncarapacho, 29S 06068/41078, 29SPB00, limestone slope with low rocks and patches of scrub, *ca* 121 m, 2011.01.29, GAH & DTH, 2011.P108, CGAH, 2 sh; *ca* 3 km NNW. of Moncarapacho (just S. of A22), 29S 060695/410771, 29SPB00, rocky limestone hillslope with patchy bushes, 131 m, 2011.02.04, GAH & DTH, 2011.P118, CGAH, 1 sh (& 3 of uncertain identity).

Cecilioides clessini, Algarve: Caneiros (S. of Ferragudo), 29S 0543/4106, 29SNB40, rocky limestone slopes with low scrub by coast, *ca* 23 m, 2014.03.23, GAH, 2014.P366, CGAH, 4 sh; 3 km SE. of Loulé, 29S 058884/410560, 29SNB80, rocky limestone slope with patchy cover of low bushes, 85 m, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH, 2011.P115, CGAH, 4 sh; *ca* 3 km W. of Querenca, 29S 0588/4117, 29SNB81, limestone scree, *ca* 146 m, 2014.03.22, GAH, 2014.P365B, CGAH, 15 sh; E. end of Rocha da Pena, 29S 05803/41234, 29SNB82, rocky limestone slope and plateau with patches of bushes, 460 m, 2011.01.28, GAH & DTH, 2011.P104, CGAH, 29 sh & 21 spm; *ca* 2 km E. of Santa Barbara de Nexe, 29S 059428/410732, 29SNB90, rocky limestone hill-slopes with patchy low scrub, 261 m, 2011.02.03, GAH & DTH, 2011.P117, CGAH, 28 sh; by N398 *ca* 2 km N. of Moncarapacho, 29S 06068/41078, 29SPB00, limestone slope with low rocks and patches of scrub, *ca* 121 m, 2011.01.29, GAH & DTH, 2011.P108, CGAH, 42 sh & 6 spm; *ca* 3 km NNW. of Moncarapacho (just S. of A22), 29S 060695/410771, 29SPB00, rocky limestone hillslope with patchy bushes, 131 m, 2011.02.04, GAH & DTH, 2011.P118, CGAH, 8 sh; Cerro da Cabeça (NE. of Olhão), 29S 06081/41075, 29SPB00, limestone crags on slope, *ca* 200 m, 2008.01.11, GAH, 2008.P59, CGAH, 35 sh; Serra de São Miguel (*ca* 4 km NW. of Moncarapacho), 29S 06043/41067, 29SPB00, rocky limestone slopes with patchy scrub and grassland, 340 m, 2011.02.04, GAH & DTH, 2011.P119, CGAH, 21 sh; just NW. of Barroqueira (*ca* 7 km NW. of Moncarapacho), 29S 060291/411092, 29SPB01, rocky limestone slopes and quarries with patchy bushes, 183 m, 2011.01.29, GAH & DTH, 2011.P107, CGAH, 14 sh & 5 spm.

